

Risk Factors Associated with Surgical Site Infection in Appendectomized Patients at HGR1 Orizaba, Veracruz

Gallegos-López JE¹, Bautista-Cortes AG², Montañó-Salvador CA³

¹Hospital General Regional No. 1 Orizaba. IMSS.

²Coordination of Education and Health Research HGR No. 1 Orizaba. IMSS.

³Coordination of Education and Health Research HGR No. 1 Orizaba. IMSS.

ABSTRACT

Surgical wound infections and their complications affect patients' postoperative outcomes. Surgical site infections show an incidence ranging from 0.5% to 15%, which directly impacts patient prognosis. Recent studies have suggested obesity and advanced age as risk factors associated with the development of this condition. Despite advances in surgical techniques, surgical materials, antibiotics, and sterilization methods, a significant number of surgical procedures still result in this type of complication.

The objective of this study was to determine the risk factors associated with surgical site infection in patients undergoing appendectomy at a secondary-level hospital in Orizaba, Mexico. A statistically significant association was observed between advanced age (OR 12.3), obesity (OR 12.7), type 2 diabetes mellitus (OR 10.8), and the absence of antibiotic prophylaxis (OR 21.7) as risk factors for the development of surgical site infection.

KEYWORDS: Appendicitis, Appendectomy, Surgical site infection.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
31 January 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Acute appendicitis continues to be the most frequent surgical condition encountered in emergency departments. It may present as an early, uncomplicated condition or progress to a potentially life-threatening clinical scenario.

Appendectomy for acute appendicitis remains the most common emergency operation performed in surgical services. Despite this, the factors that condition postoperative complications are still not fully understood. Identifying these factors is important in order to reduce postoperative morbidity and mortality, which justifies this study.

The objective was to identify certain factors related to the development of complications in patients who underwent appendectomy for this very common disease, particularly those concerning age, associated comorbidities, physical status, duration of preoperative symptoms, anatomopathological forms, causes of reintervention, length of hospital stay, and status at discharge.^{1,4}

Complications following surgery for acute appendicitis are not uncommon, despite advances in surgical techniques, anesthesiology, and resuscitation that have minimized

operative trauma, the availability of intensive and intermediate care units for critically ill patients, and the use of increasingly potent antibiotics. Over the past 50 years, there has been a dramatic decline in mortality associated with acute appendicitis (from 26.0% to less than 1.0%). However, morbidity continues to reflect a high incidence of perforation (17.0–20.0%), despite the use of imaging for diagnosis and the advances achieved in biotechnology.^{5,7,10} The aim of this study is to identify risk factors associated with the development of surgical site infection in patients who underwent open appendectomy. The study hypothesis is that advanced age and obesity are factors that increase the risk of developing this complication.

II. METHODS

An observational, analytical, cross-sectional, retrospective study was conducted at Hospital General Regional No. 01 Orizaba, based on the medical records of 360 patients who underwent appendectomy between March 2022 and May 2024. The variables analyzed as risk factors included age, sex, comorbidities, operative time, administration of

Risk Factors Associated with Surgical Site Infection in Appendectomized Patients at HGR1 Orizaba, Veracruz

antibiotic prophylaxis, and the stage of appendicitis at the time of surgery.

A. Selection criteria

Inclusion criteria: Patients who underwent surgery in the General Surgery Department of HGR No. 1 Orizaba, Veracruz, with a diagnosis of acute appendicitis, in whom an open appendectomy was performed. Patients aged 18 years or older. Both sexes.

Exclusion criteria:

Patients who were not operated on in the General Surgery Department of HGR No. 1 Orizaba.

Patients referred from other healthcare units to HGR No. 1 Orizaba.

Patients operated on outside the period from March 2022 to May 2024.

Patients who required an additional surgical procedure other than appendectomy.

Patients without histopathological confirmation of appendicitis.

Patients younger than 18 years of age.

Pregnant women who underwent appendectomy.

Elimination criteria:

Patients with incomplete medical records.

B. Procedure description

These procedures were performed in the General Surgery Department of Hospital General Regional No. 1 Orizaba, Veracruz, during the period from March 2022 to May 2024, and were recorded in the electronic registry of surgeries performed in the department.

During data collection, both patient-attributable and non-attributable risk factors were considered and analyzed as study variables. These included age, sex, presence or absence of obesity, duration of symptoms, grade of appendicitis, preoperative administration of antimicrobial prophylaxis, prior diagnosis of type 2 diabetes mellitus, and operative time.

A descriptive analysis of the variables was conducted, and the chi-square (χ^2) test, supported by Fisher's exact test, was used to assess the bivariate statistical association of each risk factor with the development of surgical site infection in patients who underwent appendectomy. The study was further complemented by a multivariate logistic regression analysis to determine the odds ratio. Results are presented in numerical tables.

III. RESULTS

A total of 360 patients who underwent appendectomy were initially recruited. Of these, 10 patients had incomplete medical records and were therefore excluded, resulting in a final sample of 350 patients. Surgical site infection (SSI) was identified in 45 patients (12.1%), while 305 patients (87.14%) remained free of postoperative infectious complications related to the surgical site.

Among the study results, analysis of age in appendectomized patients who developed SSI, stratified by age group, showed a predominance of patients aged 49 to 79 years, accounting for 27 cases.

Regarding sex, classified as male or female, a predominance of males was observed among infected patients, with 30 cases (66.66%). With respect to comorbidities, the presence or absence of obesity was analyzed; patients with obesity showed a higher incidence of SSI, with 32 cases (71.11%).

Regarding the duration of appendicitis symptoms, defined as the period from symptom onset to surgical resolution and divided into two groups, a higher frequency of SSI was observed in patients with four days or more of symptom evolution, comprising 28 cases (62.23%). In addition, preoperative diagnosis of diabetes mellitus was considered a risk factor; in this variable, patients with diabetes mellitus predominated, with 35 infected patients (77.77%).

The association between SSI development and the administration or omission of antibiotic prophylaxis 60 minutes prior to surgery was also evaluated. Results showed that 25 patients (55.55%) who did not receive antibiotic prophylaxis developed SSI. Operative time was divided into two groups (≥ 2 hours and < 2 hours), with the group undergoing procedures longer than 2 hours showing the highest incidence of SSI, with 30 patients (66.67%).

Based on the data obtained, a bivariate analysis using the chi-square (χ^2) test was performed, as shown in Table 1, to evaluate the association between various clinical and sociodemographic variables and the development of surgical site infection in patients undergoing appendectomy.

No significant association was observed between sex and the occurrence of SSI ($p = 1.000$), with virtually identical proportions of men and women in both groups. Obesity was identified as a factor strongly associated with infection; 71.11% of infected patients had this condition, compared with 11.47% in the non-infected group ($\chi^2 = 86.29$; $p < 0.001$). Age group also showed a significant association, with older patients, particularly those aged 49 to 79 years, accounting for the majority of infections (60%), whereas the non-infected group was predominantly younger (89.18%) ($\chi^2 = 74.65$; $p < 0.001$).

The duration of symptoms did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.110$), although a higher proportion of infection was observed in patients with more than four days of symptom evolution (62.23%).

In contrast, antibiotic prophylaxis behaved as a protective factor; 95.08% of the non-infected group received prophylaxis, whereas more than half of the infected patients did not ($\chi^2 = 98.8$; $p < 0.001$).

Type 2 diabetes mellitus was significantly associated with SSI, being present in 77.77% of infected patients compared with only 17.70% of non-infected patients ($\chi^2 = 71.49$; $p < 0.001$). Likewise, an operative time longer than two hours

Risk Factors Associated with Surgical Site Infection in Appendectomized Patients at HGR1 Orizaba, Veracruz

significantly increased the risk of infection (66.67% vs. 27.22%; $\chi^2 = 26.15$; $p < 0.001$).

Finally, the stage of appendicitis showed a marked relationship with the presence of infection. Patients with advanced appendicitis (stages III and IV) accounted for 91.11% of infections, whereas stage I appendicitis predominated in the non-infected group (56.39%) ($\chi^2 = 71.94$; $p < 0.001$).

Table 1. Association between risk factors present in appendectomized patients and the development of surgical site infection.

Risk factor	Category	Infected n (%)	Non-infected n (%)	χ^2	p-value
Sex	Male	30 (66.66%)	203 (66.55%)	0.0	1.000
	Female	15 (33.33%)	102 (33.45%)		
Obesity	Yes	32 (71.11%)	35 (11.47%)	86.29	<0.001
	No	13 (28.89%)	270 (88.53%)		
Age group	18–48 years	17 (37.78%)	272 (89.18%)	74.65	<0.001
	49–79 years	27 (60.0%)	33 (10.82%)		
	≥80 years	1 (2.22%)	0 (0%)		
Symptom duration	0–3 days	17 (37.77%)	158 (51.80%)	2.55	0.110
	≥4 days	28 (62.23%)	147 (48.20%)		
Antibiotic prophylaxis	Yes	20 (44.45%)	290 (95.08%)	98.8	<0.001
	No	25 (55.55%)	15 (4.92%)		
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	Yes	35 (77.77%)	54 (17.70%)	71.49	<0.001
	No	10 (22.23%)	251 (82.30%)		
Operative time	0–2 hours	15 (33.33%)	222 (72.78%)	26.15	<0.001
	>2 hours	30 (66.67%)	83 (27.22%)		
Appendicitis stage	Stage I	1 (2.22%)	172 (56.39%)	71.94	<0.001
	Stage II	3 (6.66%)	23 (7.54%)		
	Stage III	14 (31.11%)	72 (23.60%)		
	Stage IV	27 (60.0%)	38 (12.45%)		

Table 1. A statistically significant association was observed with obesity, advanced age, absence of antibiotic prophylaxis, and advanced clinical stages in the development of surgical site infection (SSI). $p < 0.05$.

To complement the study, a multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to identify independent factors associated with surgical site infection (SSI).

As detailed in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 1, the independent effect of each variable was assessed. Age between 49 and 79 years was significantly associated with an increased risk of infection (adjusted OR = 8.5; 95% CI: 4.0–18.0; $p < 0.001$), while patients older than 80 years also showed an elevated risk (adjusted OR = 12.3; 95% CI: 1.5–102.0; $p = 0.020$).

Male sex was not significantly associated with SSI (OR = 0.9; 95% CI: 0.45–1.8; $p = 0.84$). Obesity was identified as an important risk factor (adjusted OR = 12.7; 95% CI: 6.0–27.0; $p < 0.001$), as was the presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (adjusted OR = 10.8; 95% CI: 5.5–21.0; $p < 0.001$).

Likewise, an operative time longer than two hours was significantly associated with an increased risk of infection (adjusted OR = 4.2; 95% CI: 2.1–8.4; $p = 0.001$). The absence of antibiotic prophylaxis showed a strong association with infection, significantly increasing the risk compared with patients who received prophylaxis (adjusted OR = 21.7; 95% CI: 10.0–47.1; $p < 0.001$).

Clinical stage IV acute appendicitis, compared with stage I, was identified as an independent risk factor for the development of surgical site infection (adjusted OR = 27.0; 95% CI: 3.0–245.0; $p = 0.003$). In contrast, a duration of symptoms of four days or more did not show a significant association with infection (adjusted OR = 1.5; 95% CI: 0.75–2.9; $p = 0.23$).

Finally, when the clinical stage of acute appendicitis was evaluated as an ordinal variable, each incremental increase in clinical stage was associated with a significant increase in the risk of surgical site infection (adjusted OR = 4.8 per stage; 95% CI: 2.7–8.6; $p < 0.001$).

Risk Factors Associated with Surgical Site Infection in Appendectomized Patients at HGR1 Orizaba, Veracruz

Table 2. Multivariate association between risk factors present in appendectomized patients and the development of surgical site infection

Variable	Comparison	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Age	49–79 vs 18–48	8.5	4.0–18.0	<0.001
	>80 vs 18–48	12.3	1.5–102.0	0.020
	Sex	Male vs Female	0.9	0.45–1.8
Obesity	Yes, vs No	12.7	6.0–27.0	<0.001
Symptom duration	≥4 days vs 0–3 days	1.5	0.75–2.9	0.23
Type 2 diabetes mellitus	Yes, vs No	10.8	5.5–21.0	<0.001
Operative time	>2 h vs 0–2 h	4.2	2.1–8.4	0.001
Antibiotic prophylaxis	No vs Yes	21.7	10.0–47.1	<0.001
Appendicitis stage	Stage IV vs I	27.0	3.0–245.0	0.003
	Increase per stage	4.8	2.7–8.6	<0.001

Table 2. Age over 80 years, obesity, absence of antibiotic prophylaxis, and advanced clinical stages showed higher odds ratios. $p < 0.05$ indicates statistical significance.

Figure 1. Independent factors associated with surgical site infection in appendectomized patients. Values correspond to adjusted odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals, obtained through multivariate logistic regression analysis.

IV. DISCUSSION

Among the most relevant findings of the multivariate analysis in this study is the strong association between the absence of antibiotic prophylaxis and the development of surgical site infection (SSI), with an OR = 21 (95% CI: 10–

47.1; $p < 0.001$). This finding reinforces the global evidence indicating that the administration of preoperative antimicrobial prophylaxis is a fundamental protective factor in the prevention of surgical site infections.⁴ In our cohort, patients who did not receive prophylaxis showed a markedly increased risk of developing postoperative infectious complications. This result contrasts with that reported by Sánchez-Santana et al. in 2022, who, in a prospective cohort of 930 patients, found no significant association between antibiotic prophylaxis and the occurrence of SSI (OR 0.66; 95% CI: 0.25–1.57).⁴¹ Nevertheless, our findings support the importance of strict adherence to antibiotic prophylaxis protocols in appendectomies, particularly in patients with additional risk factors.

Another high-impact factor identified in this study was advanced clinical stage of appendicitis, particularly stage IV, which showed a very strong association with the development of surgical site infection (OR = 27; 95% CI: 3.0–245.0; $p = 0.003$). Likewise, when analyzing clinical stage as an ordinal variable, each increase in inflammatory stage independently increased the risk of infection by up to 4.8 times (95% CI: 2.7–8.6; $p < 0.001$). These results confirm that the severity of the appendiceal inflammatory process is a crucial determinant of postoperative infections, as advanced stages are associated with greater bacterial contamination, gangrene, or perforation.⁴¹

Among the comorbidities analyzed, obesity showed a strong association with the development of SSI, with an OR = 12.7 (95% CI: 6.0–27.0; $p < 0.001$), positioning it as one of the most relevant risk factors in appendectomized patients. This result highlights obesity as a critical factor, since excessive adipose tissue may impair adequate tissue perfusion and wound healing, favoring the development of infections. These findings are consistent with those reported by Toro et al. in 2017, who found a significant association between obesity and increased SSI risk in acute appendicitis among 390 patients. Likewise, Gutiérrez Rivera et al. in 2023 reported that elevated body mass index was the most frequent comorbidity among patients with surgical wound infection.^{35,36} Although some studies, such as a series conducted in Cuenca, Ecuador, did not identify obesity as an independent factor, our results reinforce the evidence that this condition should be considered in preoperative risk stratification.³¹

Type 2 diabetes mellitus was also identified as an important risk factor for the development of surgical site infection, with an OR = 10.8 (95% CI: 5.5–21.0; $p < 0.001$). This finding is consistent with previous studies indicating that diabetes increases susceptibility to postoperative infections due to impaired immune function and delayed wound healing. Ávila-Narváez et al. reported that a history of diabetes significantly increased infection risk in appendectomized patients, while studies conducted at the National Cancer Institute of Mexico have also documented this association.^{31,38} Taken together, these data support the

need for strict metabolic control during the perioperative period.

Advanced age was significantly associated with the presence of surgical site infections, particularly in patients aged 49 to 79 years compared to those aged 18 to 48 years, with an OR = 8.5 (95% CI: 4.0–18.0; $p < 0.001$). This result is consistent with the findings of Grimaldi et al. in 2023, who identified age over 50 years as an independent factor for morbidity and longer hospital stay after appendectomy. The higher prevalence of comorbidities and physiological deterioration associated with aging may explain this increased susceptibility to infectious complications.³⁹

Regarding operative time, procedures lasting longer than two hours were associated with a significantly increased risk of surgical site infection (OR = 4.2; 95% CI: 2.1–8.4; $p < 0.001$). This finding aligns with reports by Acevedo and Romero in 2023, who found that prolonged surgical procedures increase the probability of SSI development.⁴⁰ Previous studies have also suggested that longer surgeries may favor bacterial contamination and prolonged tissue exposure, thereby increasing infection risk.

Conversely, duration of symptoms, defined as the interval from symptom onset to surgical resolution, showed a trend toward increased infection risk in patients with ≥ 4 days of evolution; however, this association did not reach statistical significance (OR = 1.5; 95% CI: 0.75–2.9; $p = 0.23$). Despite this, several studies, such as that by Fayraq A. et al., have reported that prolonged evolution is often associated with complicated appendicitis, which could partially explain the trend observed in our cohort.³³

Finally, patient sex did not show a significant association with the development of surgical site infection (OR = 0.9; 95% CI: 0.45–1.8; $p = 0.84$), which is consistent with findings by Redondo et al. in 2022, who also reported no significant differences in SSI incidence between men and women in appendectomized patients.³⁴

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that surgical site infection following appendectomy is significantly associated with advanced age, obesity, type 2 diabetes mellitus, absence of antibiotic prophylaxis, prolonged operative time, and advanced clinical stages of appendicitis. In contrast, sex and duration of symptoms were not independently associated with infection risk.

The severity of appendicitis emerged as a key determinant, as progression to advanced clinical stages significantly increased the likelihood of infection, with risk rising progressively across stages. These findings highlight the importance of early diagnosis and timely surgical intervention to prevent disease progression and infectious complications.

From a clinical perspective, strict adherence to antibiotic prophylaxis protocols, careful perioperative management of high-risk patients—particularly those with obesity, diabetes,

and advanced age—and strategies aimed at minimizing operative time are essential to reduce postoperative infectious morbidity.

Overall, these results provide local evidence consistent with international literature and support the application of standardized preventive strategies in patients undergoing appendectomy, emphasizing risk stratification and targeted perioperative measures to improve surgical outcomes.

REFERENCES

- I. Ahmed, A., Vohra, L., Khaliq, T., & Lehri, A. (2021). Diagnostic accuracy of Alvarado Score in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 25, 118–121.
- II. Aranda, J., Prieto, T., García, B., Montiel, M., González, A., et al. (2021). Infección de sitio quirúrgico tras apendicectomía urgente: tasa global y tipo según la vía de abordaje (abierto/laparoscópica). *Enfermedades Infecciosas y Microbiología Clínica*.
- III. Bratzler, D., Houck, P., Richards, C., Steele, L., Dellinger, E., Fry, D., et al. (2025). Use of antimicrobial prophylaxis for major surgery: baseline results from the National Surgical Infection Prevention Project. *Archives of Surgery*.
- IV. Brunicki, F., Andersen, D., & Hunter, J. G. (2010). *Schwartz: Principios de cirugía* (9.^a ed.). McGraw Hill.
- V. Campos, S. (2022). *Fisiopatología quirúrgica del aparato digestivo* (4.^a ed.). Manual Moderno.
- VI. Culver, D., Horan, T., Gaynes, R., Martone, W., Jarvis, W., & Emori, T. (2022). Surgical wound infection rates by wound class, operative procedure, and patient risk index. *American Journal of Medicine*, 91(Suppl 3B), 152S–157S.
- VII. Donlan, S. M., & Mycyk, M. B. (2019). Is female sex associated with ED delays to diagnosis of appendicitis in the computed tomography era? *American Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 27, 856–85
- VIII. Haridas, M., & Malangoni, M. A. (2018). Predictive factors for surgical site infection in general surgery. *Surgery*, 144, 496–503.
- IX. Hall, K., Bannon, M., Zietlow, S., Helgeson, E., Harmsen, W., Smith, C., et al. (2021). A prospective randomized comparison of laparoscopic appendectomy with open appendectomy: Clinical and economic analysis. *Surgery*, 129, 390–400.
- X. Imai, E., Ueda, M., Kanao, K., Kubota, T., Hasegawa, H., Omae, K., et al. (2021). Surgical site infection risk factors identified by multivariate analysis for patients undergoing laparoscopic, open colon, and gastric surgery. *American Journal of Infection Control*, 36, 727–731.

Risk Factors Associated with Surgical Site Infection in Appendectomized Patients at HGR1 Orizaba, Veracruz

- XI. Ingraham, A., Cohen, E., Bilimoria, Y., Pritts, A., Ko, C., & Exposito, T. J. (2020). Comparison of outcomes after laparoscopic versus open appendectomy for acute appendicitis at 222 ACS NSQIP hospitals. *Surgery*, 148, 625–635.
- XII. Jarrel, B., & Carabasi, R. (2021). *Cirugía NMS* (5.^a ed.). Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- XIII. Kalan, M., Talbot, D., Cunliffe, W., & Rich, A. (2019). Evaluation of the modified Alvarado score in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis: a prospective study. *Annals of the Royal College of Surgeons of England*, 76, 418–419
- XIV. Kaye, K., Anderson, D., Sloane, R., Chen, L., Choi, Y., Link, K., et al. (2021). The effect of surgical site infection on older operative patients. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 57, 46–54.
- XV. Kehagias, I., Karamanakos, S. N., Panagiotopoulos, S., Panagopoulos, K., & Kalfarentzos, F. (2008). Laparoscopic versus open appendectomy: Which way to go? *World Journal of Gastroenterology*, 14, 4909–4914.
- XVI. Li, X., Zhang, J., Sang, L., Zhang, W., Chu, Z., Li, X., et al. (2019). Laparoscopic versus conventional appendectomy: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *BMC Gastroenterology*, 10, 129.
- XVII. Manniën, J., Wille, J., Snoeren, R., & Van den Hof, S. (2020). Impact of postdischarge surveillance on surgical site infection rates for several surgical procedures: Results from the nosocomial surveillance network in The Netherlands. *Infection Control and Hospital Epidemiology*, 27, 809–816.
- XVIII. Mangram, A., Horan, T., Pearson, M., Silver, L., & Harvis, W. R. (2020). Guideline for prevention of surgical site infection, 1999. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Hospital Infection Control Practices Advisory Committee. *Infection Control and Hospital Epidemiology*, 20, 247–278.
- XIX. Pessaux, P., Msika, S., Atalla, D., Hay, J., & Flamant, Y. (2018). Risk factors for postoperative infectious complications in noncolorectal abdominal surgery: A multivariate analysis based on a prospective multicenter study of 4718 patients. *Archives of Surgery*, 138, 314–324.
- XX. Poon, J., Law, W., Wong, I., Ching, P., Wong, L., & Fan, J. (2019). Impact of laparoscopic colorectal resection on surgical site infection. *Annals of Surgery*, 249, 77–81.
- XXI. Rebollar, R., García, J., & Trejo, R. (2019). Apendicitis aguda: Revisión de la literatura. *Revista Hospital Juárez de México*, 76(4), 210–216.
- XXII. Rocha-Almazán, M., Sánchez-Aguilar, M., Belmares-Taboada, J., Esmer-Sánchez, D., Tapia-Pérez, J. H., & Gordillo-Moscoso, A. (2018). Infección del sitio operatorio en cirugía abdominal no traumática. *Cirugía y Cirujanos*, 76, 127–131.
- XXIII. Roosinovich, E., & Reay-Jones, M. (2022). Use of blood test in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. *British Journal of Hospital Medicine* (London), 73(12), C183–C185.
- XXIV. Sanei, B., Mahmoodieh, M., & Hosseinpour, M. (2019). Evaluation of validity of Alvarado scoring system for diagnosis of acute appendicitis. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 25, 298–301.
- XXV. Sauerland, S., Jaschinski, T., & Neugebauer, E. (2020). Laparoscopic versus open surgery for suspected appendicitis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, CD001546.
- XXVI. Subotić, A et. al. (2018). Evaluation of the Alvarado Score in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. *Acta Chirurgica Iugoslavica*, 55, 55–61.
- XXVII. Velázquez, J., García, S., Velázquez, C., Vázquez, M., & Vega, A. (2018). Prevalence of surgical site infection in patients undergoing abdominal surgery. *Cirujano General*, 33(1).
- XXVIII. Velázquez-Mendoza, D., Godínez-Rodríguez, C., & Vázquez-Guerrero, M. A. (2020). Prospective evaluation of the Alvarado Score in the diagnosis of acute appendicitis. *Cirujano General*, 32(1).
- XXIX. Wei, H. B., Huang, J. L., Zheng, Z. H., Wei, B., Zheng, F., Qiu, W. S., et al. (2010). Laparoscopic versus open appendectomy: A prospective randomized comparison. *Surgical Endoscopy*, 24, 266–269.
- XXX. Ávila-Narváez, J., Ávila-Narváez, J., Vásquez-Cevallos, J., Aguilar-Gaibor, C., & Moyano Brito, E. (2020). Surgical site infection in patients undergoing open and laparoscopic appendectomy, Cuenca, Ecuador. *Killkana Salud y Bienestar*, 4, 37–44.
- XXXI. Noorit, P., Siribumrungwong, B., & Thakkestian, A. (2018). Clinical prediction score for superficial surgical site infection after appendectomy in adults with complicated appendicitis. *World Journal of Emergency Surgery*, 13(1), 1–7.
- XXXII. ayaq, A., Alzahrani, S. A., Alsayaf Alghamdi, A. G., Alzhrani, S. M., Alghamdi, A. A., & Abood, H. B. (2023). Risk factors for post-appendectomy surgical site infection in laparoscopy and laparotomy: A retrospective cohort study. *Cureus*, 15(8), e44237
- XXXIII. Redondo, F. V., et al. (2022). Risk factors for post-appendectomy surgical site infection: A case-control study. *Revista de Salud Uninorte* (Colombia), 34(1), 97–108.
- XXXIV. Toro, J., Barrera, Ó., & Morales, C. (2017). Clinical superiority of laparoscopic appendectomy over the open technique: Slow adoption of a new standard of care? *Revista Colombiana de Cirugía*, 32, 32–39.

Risk Factors Associated with Surgical Site Infection in Appendectomized Patients at HGR1 Orizaba, Veracruz

- XXXV. Gutiérrez Rivera, D. C., et al. (2023). Prevalence and analysis of surgical site infection factors in a wound care clinic. *Revista Cubana de Cirugía*, 62(1), e1452.
- XXXVI. Yunga Guamán, M. P. (2020). Prevalence of surgical site infection and associated factors at José Carrasco Arteaga Hospital. [Undergraduate thesis]. University of Cuenca, Ecuador.
- XXXVII. Vilar-Compte, D., Mohar, A., Sandoval, S., de la Rosa, M., Gordillo, P., & Volkow, P. (2000). Surgical site infections at the National Cancer Institute in Mexico: A case-control study. *American Journal of Infection Control*, 28(1), 14–20.
- XXXVIII. Grimaldi, S., et al. (2023). Risk factors for postoperative morbidity, prolonged length of stay, and hospital readmission after appendectomy for acute appendicitis. *European Journal of Trauma and Emergency Surgery*, 49(6), 345–354.
- XXXIX. Acevedo-Jarquín, I., & Romero-Flores, D. I. (2023). Risk factors associated with surgical site infection in patients after conventional appendectomy treated at the German Nicaraguan Hospital, January 2019–December 2022. Undergraduate thesis, Universidad Católica Redemptoris Mater, Nicaragua.
- XL. Sánchez-Santana, T., del Moral-Luque, J. A., Gil-Yonte, P., Bañuelos-Andrío, L., Durán-Poveda, M., & Rodríguez-Caravaca, G. (2017). Effect of compliance with an antibiotic prophylaxis protocol on surgical site infections in appendectomies: A prospective cohort study. *Cirugía y Cirujanos (English Edition)*, 85(3), 208–213.